

Conference Abstract

Monitoring and habitat management for weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in the Netherlands: Insights from research, citizen science, habitat management and habitat design

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Abstract

The weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) is a cryptic and vulnerable species associated with lowland aquatic systems. These systems are under severe pressure from habitat loss and hydrological alterations. Over the past century, populations in the Netherlands have declined, and the remaining dwindling populations are now fragmented, primarily due to river and brook regulation and the loss of natural flood regimes. In the Netherlands, extensive monitoring efforts have been undertaken within the framework of the National Ecological Monitoring Network (NEM), with contributions from citizen science programs and provincial Natura 2000 monitoring schemes. These efforts have enabled RAVON and Statistics Netherlands (CBS) to calculate national distribution trends for the weatherfish since 1990.

This presentation provides an overview of recent monitoring data, highlights the value of integrating ecological research with practical conservation, and showcases two case studies of habitat design and restoration (Suppl. material 1). In the first case (Rijskampen), we investigated habitat use and responses to targeted management. A shallow ditch system was constructed following an initial negative eDNA result and only one adult female being caught during intensive electrofishing, resulting in the successful

recruitment of juveniles. In the second case (Nieuwegein), a compensation area was created for *Rana arvalis*, *Pelophylax lessonae*, and *M. fossilis* (Figs 1, 2). This case has shown a consistent presence of adult and juvenile weatherfish populations annually.

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Newly excavated weatherfish ditch at the project site in Nieuwegein (Jelger Herder).

These examples demonstrate how ecological knowledge can be effectively applied to design and manage habitats that promote the long-term viability of *M. fossilis* populations.

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Figure 2. [doi](#)

Developed weatherfish habitat in one of the ditches in Nieuwegein (Jelger Herder).

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Monitoring and habitat management for weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in the Netherlands: Insights from research, citizen science, habitat management and habitat design [doi](#)

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